

INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

Scopus || Electronic journal specializing in Scopus

ISSUE 3

 Acceptance of papers **March, 2026**

**Acceptance of
papers**

Published monthly

Topics

economics,
technology, social
sciences

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AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND MASS
COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA) OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN, EFFECTIVE
FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

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The scientific electronic journal "Innovation Science and Technology" has been included in the list of scientific publications recommended for the publication of main scientific results of dissertations for the award of PhD and DSc degrees in economics and technical sciences, in accordance with the Resolution No. 370 of the Presidium of the Higher Attestation Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated May 8, 2025.

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DIRECTIONS FOR INCREASING HOUSEHOLD INCOMES BASED ON FOREIGN EXPERIENCE

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Abstract: This article analyzes various mechanisms for increasing household incomes and expanding entrepreneurial activity in Uzbekistan based on foreign experience. The study examines mechanisms aimed at promoting entrepreneurship that are being implemented in developed and developing countries in the context of globalization. In particular, measures to increase labor productivity, expand financial services, invest in human capital, and support the development of small business and entrepreneurship are considered. Based on the results obtained during the analysis, mechanisms for adapting foreign experience to strengthen household entrepreneurship, diversify the structure of household incomes, and improve public welfare were developed. In addition, scientific recommendations aimed at enhancing the effectiveness of income growth policies were proposed.

Key words: Household income, foreign experience, women's entrepreneurship, small and medium-sized enterprises, savings, formal employment, personal subsidiary farming, agriculture.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern economic system, countries around the world consider improving the welfare of the population, expanding the income base of households, and achieving sustainable economic growth as one of the highest priorities. The stability of household incomes currently serves as an important factor contributing to the positive dynamics of many macroeconomic indicators. Household income is one of the key determinants that define the quality of life, well-being, social stability, and consumption levels of the population. Therefore, studying foreign experiences in this field and adapting their effective approaches to national conditions is of great importance in the process of developing this sector.

International experience shows that increasing household incomes is not limited solely to raising wage levels. This process also includes creating a favorable investment climate, establishing the necessary conditions for expanding entrepreneurial activity, providing tax incentives, increasing employment levels, attracting investments to social sectors, expanding access to financial services, and improving the financial literacy of the population. According to studies conducted by the International Labour Organization and the World Bank, stable employment and the availability of a skilled labor force are key factors ensuring the sustainable growth of household incomes¹. In developing countries, scientific research has demonstrated that promoting self-employment, developing microfinance systems, and expanding social protection programs contribute significantly to the consistent growth of household incomes². For instance, countries such as Turkey, South Korea, and Malaysia have achieved substantial increases in household incomes through the development of entrepreneurial activities³.

In Uzbekistan, comprehensive economic reforms are currently being implemented to increase household incomes, support entrepreneurial activities, and improve the welfare of the population. In particular, the Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022–2026 pays special attention to increasing employment, reducing poverty levels, preventing unequal distribution of incomes, and expanding the income base of the population. Within the framework of this strategy, priority tasks have been defined to achieve positive results in these areas⁴.

1 World Bank. World Development Report: Jobs. Washington DC, 2018.

2 ILO. Global Employment Trends. Geneva, 2020.

3 Asian Development Bank. Inclusive Growth in Asia. Manila, 2017.

4 Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60. "On the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026." <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/-5841063>

At the regional level, based on the decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan aimed at reducing poverty and ensuring employment of the population, the “mahalla-based working system” has been introduced and mechanisms for increasing household incomes have been developed. This system represents a governance mechanism aimed at identifying and addressing the problems of the population at the community (mahalla) level⁵. Through the implementation of comprehensive measures in areas such as employment promotion, development of entrepreneurial activities, vocational training, and social protection, this system contributes to increasing the income levels of the population.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The issue of expanding the income base of households has been widely discussed in economic literature. The main factors for addressing this issue include ensuring employment, increasing labor productivity, developing human capital, and supporting small business and entrepreneurship.

In foreign practice, five key directions are generally identified for increasing household incomes. These include increasing women’s economic participation, promoting self-employment and entrepreneurship, developing agriculture, labor migration and remittances, as well as increasing household savings⁶.

It is appropriate to consider several studies conducted in this area. For example, according to the results of a study conducted in China by D. Coady and his colleagues in 2001, it was found that increased participation of women in economic activities in rural areas led to a 19.4–28 percent increase in household incomes. In addition, the personal incomes of women participating in the program increased by 169 percent.

In 2023, Y. Pasichnyk and colleagues conducted research using Ukraine as a case study and identified several key factors influencing the growth of household incomes. However, the degree of influence of these factors was not clearly quantified, which limits the ability to fully assess their effectiveness.

Research led by Liliya Kluchnyk examined the experience of European countries. In this study, particular attention was given to household savings rates, which were found to range from 59 percent to 85 percent. The researchers evaluated these savings as an important internal financial resource that contributes to increasing household incomes. However, the mechanisms for implementing these processes in practice were not sufficiently explained⁷.

According to a study conducted in 2023 by Uzbek economist Abdulla Ashurov and his colleagues, personal subsidiary farms represent an important source of income for approximately 500 million small households in the economies of developing countries. They also emphasized that these farms provide nearly 80 percent of household consumption needs⁸.

In 2024, A. T. Khairutdinov analyzed the economies of developed countries and noted that increasing household incomes is considered one of the priority directions of socio-economic policy in many states⁹.

In general, a significant number of scientific studies have been conducted on expanding the income base of households in the existing literature. However, the strategies and mechanisms for implementing these research results in practice have not been sufficiently explored. This indicates the need for deeper analysis of foreign experiences, their adaptation to national economic conditions, and further scientific research in this field.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study, a mixed research approach was applied and secondary data sources were used to examine the mechanisms of foreign experience in increasing household incomes. During the research process, data from the World Bank, the International Labour Organization, and the OECD were analyzed. In addition, foreign and domestic scientific articles, as well as presidential decrees and resolutions aimed at developing households in Uzbekistan, were also examined.

In the analysis process, the studied foreign experiences were compared using the comparative analysis method. Furthermore, methods such as statistical data generalization, systematic analysis, and logical comparison were applied. This methodological approach helps identify effective mechanisms for increasing household incomes and assess the possibilities of applying them within the conditions of the national economy.

5 Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF–55 and Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ–385 on measures aimed at reducing poverty and ensuring employment. <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/-6218489>

6 Pasichnyk Y., et al. Household income growth mechanisms: foreign experience. – 2023.

7 Coady D., Grosh M., Hoddinott J. Targeting outcomes redux. World Bank, 2001.

8 Pasichnyk Y., et al. Income stability factors in Ukraine. – 2023.

9 Ashurov A., et al. Personal subsidiary farms and household income. – 2023.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

During the study of foreign experiences, it can be observed that increasing household incomes represents a complex system that is associated not only with economic reforms but also with social and institutional factors. Based on the analyzed international practices, several key directions can be identified.

First, encouraging women's economic participation plays an important role in increasing household incomes. Programs aimed at promoting gender equality implemented in China have demonstrated that the growth of women's economic and social activity significantly contributes to the increase in household incomes¹⁰.

Second, studies conducted in rural areas of Ukraine during the period 2016–2021 analyzed the structure of household incomes. The observations revealed that during this period the share of income obtained through wages increased, while income derived from the sale of agricultural products declined. In addition, the application of state social standards at the national level in Ukraine was also examined. According to the results of the analysis:

- the minimum subsistence level per capita increased by 1.68 times,
- the minimum wage increased by 4.19 times,
- social assistance provided to low-income families increased by 3.59 times.

The results of this study indicate that the development of business activities, support for the social sector, and the improvement of existing infrastructure are important factors in increasing household incomes¹¹.

Third, the development of small and medium-sized enterprises is directly related to the growth of household incomes. The experience of Kyrgyzstan demonstrates that rising income levels encourage households to expand their entrepreneurial activities and lead to an increase in savings¹².

Fourth, promoting savings plays a significant role in expanding the income base of households. In most European countries, a large proportion of the population actively uses savings practices, which contributes to financial stability. Partial tax exemptions on savings and increasing public trust in the financial system help expand the financial resources of households¹³.

Fifth, the development of agriculture and personal subsidiary farming allows households to diversify their income sources. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), agriculture plays a crucial role in producing more than half of the basic food products in developing countries¹⁴.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The analysis of foreign experience shows that mechanisms aimed at increasing household incomes can also produce effective results in Uzbekistan. However, these approaches should be adapted to the economic and social system of the country. At the same time, it is important to take into account demographic factors, labor resources, the level of resource availability in different regions, as well as disparities in income distribution.

Based on the studied international practices, several key mechanisms should be emphasized to increase household incomes in Uzbekistan. First, supporting women's entrepreneurship is of great importance, including the development of specialized business training programs and initiatives for women, as well as the provision of tax incentives. In addition, encouraging formal employment and improving the wage system can expand stable sources of income for the population.

Furthermore, supporting the development of small and medium-sized enterprises and increasing their share in the national economy play an important role in raising household incomes. The development of the household savings system and the expansion of opportunities for the population to access financial resources also contribute to ensuring income stability.

At the same time, the development of the agricultural sector, attracting investments to this field, and introducing modern technologies will expand the opportunities for diversifying household incomes. The implementation of these recommendations in practice will contribute to ensuring the sustainable growth of household incomes, improving the living standards of the population, and strengthening socio-economic stability in the country.

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¹¹ Y. Pasichnyk, O. Biletska, Scientific Notes of Ostroh Academy National University, «Economics» Series, 2023.

¹² E.V. Taranova, Gulzat Rysaliev, Mairambubu Razhapaeva, Economics of Development, 2024.

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Proofreader: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Layout and Designer: Oloviddin Sobir ugli

2026. № 3

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